

Keywords:

#Pundit, #webannotationtool, #Net7,
#informationgathering, #note-taking
#Structuredannotations, #EOSCmarketplace

Pundit: Empowering Web Annotation for Researchers and Beyond

Enhancing Information Gathering, Organization, and Collaboration

The Project Involved

The Italian company Net7 (<https://netseven.it>) has been developing, since 2011, the web annotation tool Pundit (<https://thepund.it>). Pundit helps users, in particular researchers and scholars, to create annotations, that is, to easily and effectively "take notes" on web documents like HTML pages and PDF files.

The Challenge

Many people on the web, including researchers, students, and everyday users, often face three key challenges. They struggle to:

- Gather important information from the web by taking notes.
- Find a single place to keep and manage these notes.
- Make these notes more structured and easy to reuse.

These challenges aren't limited to experts; they affect anyone trying to make the most of online information. So, whether you're a student doing research or just someone looking for information online, these difficulties are something many of us encounter.

Luca De Santis

Chief Technology Officer at NetSeven

"Pundit, developed by the Italian company Net7 since 2011, is a web annotation tool that simplifies the process of 'taking notes' on web documents, offering structured and reusable annotations for researchers, scholars, and everyday users."

EOSC service or tool used

Pundit can be an answer to these issues. It is a cloud service that allows users to "take notes" on web documents, like a web page or a PDF file. It consists of a set of components, amongst them the Annotator, a free extension for the Google Chrome browser used by users to create annotations. Annotations can be highlights of text parts, comments, tags but also semantic annotations, real RDF triples (subject -> predicate -> object) to specify formal, structured and reusable statements associated to the annotated content.

Pundit can be found on the EOSC: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pundit-a-semantic-powered-web-annotation-service>

Useful tips & tricks

Pundit is free to use. You can go to its web site <https://thepund.it>, register, download the Chrome extension and start to annotate the web. Your annotations will be available in the the Pundit web app and can be easily exported in open formats, to encourage their maximum reuse.

The Research Community

Currently Pundit has almost 20.000 registered users, mostly scholars, especially those belonging to the SSH domain. The 100 most active users in the last 12 months created about 13.000 annotations.

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Benefits and impact

The inclusion of Pundit in the EOSC marketplace has had a profound impact on its visibility and potential utilization. Previously, Pundit was primarily recognized within the SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) domain. However, its presence in the EOSC marketplace has broadened its reach, making it accessible and relevant to a wider audience beyond SSH. Additionally, active involvement in the EOSC DIH pilot initiative has opened new horizons. It has prompted a thorough exploration of alternative business models and diverse use cases for Pundit. These efforts aim to unlock its potential in areas such as training artificial intelligence models for text processing, transcending its original scope and contributing to a more versatile and extensive adoption of the tool.

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC is and will be even more significantly in the future, the one-stop-shop for European researchers in search of solutions to solve their problems and to improve the way they work. Being there is therefore essential for a solution like Pundit, which has been mostly implemented through EU funded research projects and has been designed from day one to support research activities.

Across disciplines

Albeit Pundit is totally agnostic respect the scientific domain in which it is applied, it is also true that historically the SSH domain has been the most receptive in using a tool "to take notes on the web". SSH is itself a wide and cross-disciplinary domain, with at least 27 branches of knowledge, spanning from Archeology to Economy, from Social Sciences to Art and Art History. Finally Pundit encourages the sharing of annotations amongst users, facilitating collaborations, possibly also in a multidisciplinary way.

Useful material related to this story

netseven.it

thepund.it

Limitations and future improvement

Pundit is continuously growing with new features. One area that we are actively working on is to potentiate the support of Semantic Web features, allowing users to annotate by using multiple ontologies and also by defining their own personal ontologies.

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